

Development of Alumina as an Ion-Exchanger and Its Applications. Part—I*

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Alumina samples of various surface pH, prepared by treating Brockmann alumina with varying concentration of hydrochloric acid, have been employed as substrate. The samples have been used for adsorption-desorption of 2:4-dinitrophenol and picric acid from water; under a variety of conditions of concentration, time, temperature and solvents. The adsorption is found to be pH dependent; and the favourable range is pH 3.25-5.5. The greater degree of adsorption in short time-interval (10-30 min), low values of heat of adsorption (-1 to -5 K cal/mole), and easy desorption have been interpreted by ion-exchange mechanism. The two solutes have been separated by column chromatography.

THE surface of alumina powder used for chromatography, consisting largely of γ - Al_2O_3 with a little of the monohydrate, has an electrostatic charge in water, normally positive. The hydrated surface may ionise in one of the two ways; depending upon the nature of the bond holding the hydroxyl group to the surface^{1,2}. Thus:

Pretreatment of the material with an acid, like hydrochloric acid, covers the surface with the acid anions, that may be either covalently bound or present ionically (hydrated)³:

Fuller³ attributes the apparent ion-exchange capacity due to amphoteric reaction of hydroxyl groups, contained in the structure of alumina, as shown below:

It is clear that the upper reactions, producing anion-exchange properties, are favoured by low pH; whereas the lower reactions, favoured by high pH,

result in cation-exchange characteristics. The rates of ion-exchange on alumina are usually sufficiently rapid but complex, and markedly dependent on pH.⁴

Experimental

Substrate:

Alumina samples of surface pH 1.3-7.5 were prepared by treating Brockmann alumina (S. Merck, India, Activity II, particle size 100-400 mesh) with varying concentration of HCl-acid (Table 1). The original sample had pH 8.6.

The Brockmann sample (100 g), after heating at 150° for 12 hr, was covered separately with different concentrations of HCl (200 ml) at 30°. The samples were shaken mechanically for different periods. Afterwards, the samples were allowed to stand for 10 min more, and the clear liquid decanted. The samples were washed repeatedly with distilled water till the washings had pH as shown in the Table. The wash-liquid was removed, the samples dried at 150° for 12 hr, sieved and stored. Except for alumina of pH 7.5, attempt was made to remove the adhering acid, if any.

The sample of pH 8.0 was prepared by the same technique except that the original sample was washed with distilled water only.

For pH determinations, alumina (1.0 g) was shaken with distilled water (100 ml) at 30°, kept for

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10 min, and pH of the supernatant liquid determined with "Systronics" pH meter (Type 322, Sl. No. 512). The accuracy of the determinations is $\pm 1\%$.

show the process to be exothermic, and the isosteric heats of adsorption is calculated to be -1 to -5 k cal/mole.

TABLE 1—CONDITIONS FOR THE PREPARATION OF ALUMINA OF VARYING pH

pH of alumina prepared	Initial amount of alumina Time of contact after shaking	Volume of water and hydrochloric acid added	Period of mechanical shaking	pH of the wash-liquid
8.0	100 g, pH 8.6 10 min	200 ml of distilled water	20 min	8.5-9.0
7.5	...	200 ml of 0.0125 N-hydrochloric acid	50 min	8.0-8.5
7.0	...	200 ml of 0.025 N-hydrochloric acid	20 min	8.0-8.5
6.5	...	200 ml of 0.025 N-hydrochloric acid	50 min	7.5-8.0
6.0	...	100 ml water + 200 ml of 0.25 N-hydrochloric acid	20 min	7.0-7.5
5.5	...	100 ml water + 200 ml of 0.05 N-hydrochloric acid	50 min	6.5-7.0
5.0	...	200 ml of 0.05 N-hydrochloric acid	20 min	6.0-6.5
4.5	...	200 ml of 0.05 N-hydrochloric acid	50 min	5.5-6.0
4.0	...	200 ml of 0.1 N-hydrochloric acid	20 min	5.0-5.5
3.5	...	200 ml of 0.2 N-hydrochloric acid	20 min	4.5-5.0

Alumina of pH 1.8, 2.0, 2.45 and 8.25 were prepared from alumina of pH 8.5 by adding varying concentration of hydrochloric acid.

Solutes :

2 : 4-Dinitrophenol and picric acid (BDH) recrystallised from ethanol-water (1 : 1, V/V) were used as solutes. From the stock solution of the nitrophenols (0.1 g/l) in water, 10-80 ml solutions were withdrawn, and diluted to 100 ml. Further, out of these diluted solutions, 5 ml were withdrawn, mixed with 5 ml of 0.1N caustic soda, diluted to 30 ml, and estimated at 400 nm with "Spekol spectrophotometer" (Carl-Zeiss). The reproducibility of the spectral measurements are $\pm 0.5\%$.

For adsorption studies, alumina (0.25 g) was transferred to a number of 25 ml-volumetric flasks, the nitrophenol solution (10-80 ml) added, shaken and kept in thermostat. The flasks were shaken periodically, and after a specified period, 5 ml of the aliquot withdrawn, centrifuged and estimated. Temperatures are reported in $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Adsorption Vs Time and Temperature :

The variation of adsorption as a function of time (30 min-24 hr) was conducted at $30 \pm 1^{\circ}$. The process appears to be quite fast in the initial stages (50 % adsorption in 30 min), and equilibrium reaches in 24 hr. However, the extent of adsorption of picric acid decreases with time, and the equilibrium appears to be attained in 24 hr. The isotherms are of S_1 -type. The temperature effect studies (30° - 60°)

Adsorption Vs pH :

The results of change in the nature of adsorption with pH are shown in Figs. 1-4. It is observed that the affinity of the solutes for the substrates gradually increases in the pH range 2.0-5.5, and then decreases till it drops to zero at pH 8.6. The isotherms are S_1 -shaped at lower pH values with a tendency to assume a linear shape with increase in pH.

Fig. 1. Adsorption isotherms of 2 : 4 DNP from ag. soln. on alumina of varying pH.

Desorption Studies :

Desorption behaviour of the two nitrophenols adsorbed on alumina of various pH ($30 \pm 1^{\circ}$, 24 hr) was tested with a number of organic solvent-water mixtures and aq inorganic electrolytes (NaCl , Na_2SO_4 and Na_3PO_4). The procedure of desorption followed is to first allow the solute solution to equilibrate with the adsorbent for 24 hr. The substrate was allowed to settle, and the solute (12.5 ml)

Fig. 2. Adsorption isotherms of 2 : 4 DNP from ag. soln. on alumina of varying pH.

Fig. 3. Adsorption isotherms of picric acid from ag. soln. on alumina.

were pipetted-out from each flask, centrifuged and estimated. The flasks with 12.5 ml nitrophenol solution were made up to the mark by adding the desorbing solvent (12.5 ml) immediately, and thermostated at 30° for 24 hr. After this period, 12.5 ml solute solution were withdrawn and estimated (first dilution). The solutions left in the flasks were again given the same treatment (second dilution).

The study reveals that in the pH range 3.5-6.5, the solutes are completely desorbed with aqueous pyridine (1 : 4 V/V), M/100-NaCl, Na₂SO₄, Na₃PO₄ and NaOH. Desorption efficacy of the other desorbents is in the order :

	Dioxane-water (1 : 1)	Glycerine-water (1 : 4)	Dimethyl formamide-water (1 : 4)...all in V/V
2 : 4-DNP	83%	51%	41%
Picric Acid	47%	46%	34%

Results and Discussion

Adsorption of an organic ion may be controlled by Van der Waals' forces and electrical forces operating on the charged groups. If the adsorbent is ionic, the possibility of ion-exchange cannot be ruled out. Based on the observations of the study, it may be suggested that adsorption of the two nitrophenols may take place predominantly by ion-exchange, as shown by :

(i) The greater degree of adsorption in a short time-interval, and very low values of heat of adsorption⁶.

(ii) *pH and Adsorption* : The solutes in their favourable range of adsorption (pH 3.25-5.5) are essentially in the ionic state, and appear to be the principal adsorbing species. pH 5.5 is the optimum pH where adsorption is maximum, although not 100%. At pH < 5.5 concentration of the chloride

Fig. 4. Adsorption isotherms of picric acid from ag. soln. on alumina.

ions on the substrate surface increases, and the ionic species responsible for adsorption decrease. The behaviour is so prominent that 2:4-DNP and picric acid have no affinity for alumina at pH 2.0 and 1.3 respectively (k_a of 2:4-DNP = 1.0×10^{-4} and that of picric acid is 4.2×10^{-1}). At pH > 5.5, the proportion of exchangeable chloride decreases, so-much-so that it drops to zero at pH 8.6.

The S_1 -type isotherms (Figs. 1-4), indicating 'cooperative adsorption' and significant adsorbate-adsorbate interactions, may be due to stacking of the molecules with a tilted configuration, which also permits orbital-overlapping (weak interaction)⁶.

(iii) Desorption :

The degree of reversibility of the sorption reaction for the nitrophenols on alumina by inorganic electrolytes also points to the ion-exchange mechanism. The sorption equilibrium measurements made (pH 3.5-6.5) in presence of NaCl, Na_2SO_4 and Na_3PO_4 (M/100, 1.0 ml) indicate a significant salt effect. No adsorption occurs in their presence. It appears that the presence of inorganic anion might, by a competition effect, reduce the amount of solute taken up⁷. The anions (Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-}), having greater affinity for the surface, are being retained.

It is also likely that after primary adsorption, the solutes may diffuse into the micropores of alumina, and the system may be reversible but very slowly.

The desorption behaviour with organic solvent-water mixtures is typical. It is likely that the interfacial surface tension is being affected but the subject needs further work.

Conclusion

The results of this investigation show that ion-exchange capacity of alumina can be suitably evoked by pretreatment with an acid like hydrochloric acid. The nitrophenols are adsorbed by alumina mainly by ion-exchange with surface inorganic anions, and partly by weak interactions. It is now seen that this fact has practical importance also because a greater proportion of the solutes is readily desorbed in presence of inorganic anions of high basicity. Thus, mixture of the two nitrophenols from benzene was separated on an alumina column (12×1 cm, pH 5.5) with dioxane-water (4 : 1, V/V) and dioxane-buffer of pH 5.5 (1 : 1, V/V) as eluents.

References

1. S. N. TEWARI and S. GHOSH, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. (India)*, 1952, 21A, 41; *Kolloid Z.*, 1954, 138, 93.
2. D. J. O'CONNOR and A. S. BUCHANAN, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, 52, 229.
3. M. J. FULLER, *Chromatographic Review*, 1971, 14, 45.
4. S. C. CHURMS, *J. Soc. Afr. Chem. Inst.*, 1966, 19, 108.
5. C. H. GILES, H. V. MEHTA, C. E. STEWART and S. M. K. RAHMAN, *J. Appl. Chem. (London)*, 1959, 9, 457.
6. C. H. GILES, D. SMITH and A. HUITSON, *J. of Colloid and Interface Sci.*, 1974, 47, 755, 766.
7. C. H. GILES and K. V. DATYE, *Trans of the Inst. of Metal Finishing*, 1963, 40, 113.